

Supplementary Information for:

Phylogenetic conflict between species tree and maternally inherited gene trees in a clade of *Emberiza* buntings (Aves: Emberizidae)

Authors

Dezhi Zhang¹, Huishang She¹, Shangyu Wang^{1,2}, Haitao Wang³, Shi Li⁴, Yalin Cheng¹, Gang Song¹, Chenxi Jia¹, Yanhua Qu¹, Frank E. Rheindt⁵, Urban Olsson^{6,7}, Per Alström^{1,8} and Fumin Lei^{1,2*}

¹Key Laboratory of Zoological Systematics and Evolution, Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, 100101 Beijing, China.

²College of Life Sciences, University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, 100049 Beijing, China.

³School of Life Sciences, Jilin Key Laboratory of Animal Resource Conservation and Utilization, Northeast Normal University, Changchun 130024, China.

⁴College of Animal Science and Technology, Jilin Agricultural University, Changchun 130118, China.

⁵Department of Biological Sciences, National University of Singapore, Singapore 117543, Republic of Singapore.

⁶Department of Biology and Environmental Science, University of Gothenburg, Box 463, SE-405 30 Gothenburg, Sweden.

⁷Gothenburg Global Biodiversity Centre, Box 461, SE-405 30 Gothenburg, Sweden.

⁸Animal Ecology, Department of Ecology and Genetics, Evolutionary Biology Centre, Uppsala University, Norbyvägen 18 D, SE-752 36 Uppsala, Sweden.

*To whom correspondence may be addressed. Email: leifm@ioz.ac.cn.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling, resequencing and variant calling

We sampled a total of 41 individuals, including 9 *E. godlewskii* (5 males and 4 females) collected in China, 11 *E. cia* (7 males and 4 females) from Tajikistan, 10 *E. cioides* (8 males and 2 females) from China, 10 *E. jankowskii* (3 males and 7 females) from China and 1 female *E. stewarti* from China (Fig. 2; Table S1). For *E. jankowskii*, all birds were released after blood samples had been collected, whereas for the other species, muscle tissues were used. Only specimens of *E. cia* were prepared as study skins following sample collection. Specimens were stored at the National Zoological Museum, Institute of Zoology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China. *Emberiza stewarti* was used as the outgroup species based on Alström et al. (2008), Päckert et al. (2015) and Cai et al. (2021). According to previous analyses using combined mitochondrial and nuclear genes, *E. stewarti* was estimated to have diverged from the four focal species at around 5.5 Mya (Cai et al. 2021) or about 8.5 Mya (Päckert et al. 2015). We extracted genomic DNA from tissue or blood samples using the QIAGEN DNeasy[®] Blood & Tissue Kit according to the manufacturer's instructions. We prepared DNA sequencing libraries with ~350 base pair (bp) insertions according to the manufacturer's protocols, and sequenced them on an Illumina Novaseq 6000 platform with a paired-end (PE) read length of 150 bp. Briefly, total DNA was sheared by ultrasonication to select ~350 bp fragments, and libraries for each sample were prepared for sequencing after adapter ligation and PCR amplification. The indexed libraries were pooled and then sequenced to obtain 150 bp paired end reads. The target sequence data was 15 Gb for each sample. Raw reads were obtained after demultiplexing. The above procedures of DNA library preparation and sequencing were conducted by Berry Genomics (Beijing, China). Raw reads were quality-controlled to remove adapter sequences, low-quality reads (those with over 50% of bases having Phred quality scores <3) and poly-N reads (those with 3% unidentified nucleotides) in fastp 0.20.0 (Chen et al. 2018).

Quality controlled reads of all 41 samples were mapped to the reference genome of a congeneric species, *E. elegans* (GenBank genome assembly accession:

GCA_022818055.1; Zhang et al. 2023) using BWA 0.7.12 (Li and Durbin 2009). The divergence time between *E. elegans* and the four focal species was estimated at ~8 (Cai et al. 2021) or ~12 (Päckert et al. 2015) million years (My). Variants were called in SAMtools 0.1.19 (Li et al. 2009) using the “mpileup” module after removing polymerase chain reaction (PCR) duplicates. Mapping to the reference genome and removing PCR duplicates resulted in an average sequencing depth of 15.8 (Table S1). Sequencing depths for each sample were estimated using BEDtools 2.27 (Quinlan and Hall 2010) with the “genomecov” function based on the PCR duplicate removed BAM file. Single-nucleotide variants (SNVs) were filtered using VCFtools 0.1.12b (Danecek et al. 2011) using the following criteria: i) quality value ≥ 30 ; ii) genotype depth ≥ 8 ; iii) only biallelic SNVs were retained; iv) SNVs with missing genotypes were deleted; v) SNVs different in the reference species but homogeneous within the 41 samples were removed.

Testing for the most likely phylogeny using fastsimcoal2

A total of 12 demographic models were tested (Fig. S1). If tree 1 [((((southern *E. godlewskii*, northern *E. godlewskii*), *E. cia*), *E. cioides*), *E. jankowskii*)] represents the true species tree, gene flow between *E. cia* and southern *E. godlewskii* (model 1-1 in Fig. S1) and between *E. cia* and northern *E. godlewskii* (model 1-2 in Fig. S1), combined with incomplete lineage sorting (ILS), may lead to the occurrence of tree 2 and tree 3; these two types of gene flow may exist simultaneously (model 1-3 in Fig. S1); in the absence of gene flow, tree 2 and tree 3 can also occur due to ILS alone (model 1-4 in Fig. S1). Similarly, we set up four other models to test if tree 2 or tree 3 represents the true species tree (Fig. S1).

An average generation time of 2.1 years for these *Emberiza* species (Bird et al. 2020) and an average passeriform mutation rate of 0.33% per My (Zhang et al. 2014) were applied. Based on the divergence time estimations (Fig. 2c), the root divergence between *E. cia* and *E. godlewskii* was estimated at about 1 million years (~500,000 generations). Therefore, we set a search range of T10 (see Fig. S1) between 10,000 to 500,000 generations, T20 (see Fig. S1) from T10 + 10,000 to T10 + 200,000 generations,

T30 (divergence time between *E. cioides* and the former two species) from 785,714 to 847,619 generations, and T40 (divergence time between *E. jankowskii* and the former three species) from 1,085,714 to 1,180,952 generations, for all models. The effective population sizes (θ in Fig. S1) for all modern and ancestral populations were set between 1,000 and 10,000,000. We set a search range of gene flow from 0.0000001 to 0.1 for both directions. We ran fastsimcoal2 with 300,000 simulations ($-n = 300,000$) and 20 cycles ($-L = 20$) and performed 10 independent runs for each model to obtain the best run with the highest likelihood values. We compared values of the Akaike information criterion of each model.

Phylogenetic analysis of mitochondrial DNA

A complete mitochondrial sequence of *E. fucata* (GenBank accession: NC_033338.1) was used as reference. All ambiguous sites of the initial assembly were converted to homozygous sites using the command “miraconvert” in MIRA 4.0.1 (Chevreux et al. 1999). All mitochondrial sequences were aligned using mafft 7.464 (Nakamura et al. 2018) with the command “--adjustdirection”. Gblocks 0.91b (Talavera and Castresana 2007) was used under default parameters to retain the conserved sequences for downstream phylogenetic analysis. The length of the mitochondrial alignment was 16,337 bp. A total of 1,143 bp cytochrome *b* (*cytb*) gene sequence was identified by aligning all the mitochondrial sequences to the *cytb* sequence of *E. godlewskii* (GenBank accession: EU325760.1) using an online alignment web server (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/Tools/msa/clustalo/>) (Madeira et al. 2019) with default parameters. The *cytb* alignment and the rest of the mitochondrial sequences were treated as two separate partitions for phylogenetic inference and divergence time estimation in BEAST 2.4.5 (Bouckaert et al. 2014). We set the priors to birth-death model. Ten million iterations were carried out while sampling every 1,000 generations. We utilized a GTR model and applied a clock rate of 2.1% per My for the *cytb* gene (Weir and Schluter 2008), while leaving the evolutionary rates of other parts to be estimated. The effective sample sizes (ESS) for all the parameters were checked for convergence in Tracer 1.6 (<https://github.com/beast-dev/tracer/releases>), ensuring that

all ESSs were higher than 400. A consensus tree was generated using TreeAnnotator 1.8 with a 10% burn-in, well after stationarity had been reached, and was visualized in FigTree 1.3.1 (<http://tree.bio.ed.ac.uk/software/figtree/>).

Detection of non-recombining W chromosome (NRW) sequences

We used SOAPdenovo 2.04 (Luo et al. 2012) to assemble scaffold-level genome sequences for female individuals from each of the 6 *Emberiza* clades using default parameters with a k-mer value of 23. Given the lower substitution rate of the W chromosome as compared to autosomes (Irwin 2018; Smeds et al. 2015), longer W-linked sequences are needed to reconstruct the phylogeny of closely related species. We randomly selected one male sample from each of the 5 clades (except for the outgroup) and generated a super pseudo-male sample by merging upstream and downstream sequencing reads, respectively, for these 5 samples. We then mapped this super pseudo-male sample to each corresponding female assembly using BWA 0.7.12 (Li and Durbin 2009). We used BEDtools 2.27 (Quinlan and Hall 2010) to estimate the coverage for each scaffold. Scaffolds with an average sequencing depth ≤ 1 (close to zero) and ≥ 500 bp were retained and further aligned to the potential NRW sequences of *Taeniopygia guttata* (GenBank assembly accession: GCA_008822115.3). To identify the NRW sequences of *T. guttata*, we used the known NRW sequences of *Ficedula albicollis* (~6.9 Mb with 1,807 scaffolds) (GenBank assembly accession: GCA_900067835.1; Smeds et al. 2015) to align to the W chromosome of *T. guttata* (~20.8 Mb with 1 scaffold) in NGenomeSyn 1.30 (<https://github.com/Hewm2008/NGenomeSyn>) with “-MinAlgLen 500”. The pseudo-autosomal regions (PARs) of the W chromosome in birds that maintain recombination with the Z chromosome are usually on one end of the W chromosome. Therefore, the range between the farthest aligned points on the W chromosome of *T. guttata* was considered as the potential NRW sequences (~20.3 Mb; Fig. S7).

The longest part of the scaffolds that successfully mapped to the NRW sequences of *T. guttata* was retained as the final NRW sequences for each female. To obtain homologous sequences, the female of southern *E. godlewskii* was aligned to the

remaining individuals one by one using BLAST+ 2.2.26 with the command “-max_target_seqs 1 -evalue 1e-10 -outfmt 6”. Sequences that appeared in at least 5 individuals were retained as candidate homologous sequences. These homologous NRW sequences were aligned using mafft 7.464 (Nakamura et al. 2018) with the command “--adjustdirection”. We then used Gblocks 0.91b (Talavera and Castresana 2007) to retain the final sequences for downstream analysis with the command “-b1=5 -t=d”. As the avian NRW contains much more DNA repeats than autosomes (Smeds et al. 2015), the repeat regions for each concatenated NRW sequence were hard-masked using repeatMasker 4.1.1 (<https://www.repeatmasker.org/>) with the command “-species Aves” to alleviate the effects of repeat sequences on phylogenetic reconstruction.

A total of 38,994 bp NRW sequences were concatenated and used to conduct phylogenetic analysis in BEAST 2.4.5 (Bouckaert et al. 2014) with the same settings as described above. The mutation rate of the Z chromosome has been reported to be 1.1 times higher than that of autosomes (Irwin 2018), while the synonymous substitution rate (ds) has been found to be 1.57 times higher for the Z chromosome than for the W chromosome (Smeds et al. 2015). Using an average mutation rate of 0.0033 per My for passerines (Zhang et al. 2014), we inferred a rough mutation rate of 0.00231 per My for the W chromosome and applied it as the clock rate in the BEAST analysis. We ensured that all ESSs of parameters were higher than 300 in Tracer 1.6 (<https://github.com/beast-dev/tracer/releases>). The consensus tree was generated in TreeAnnotator 1.8 with a 10% burn-in and was visualized in FigTree 1.3.1 (<http://tree.bio.ed.ac.uk/software/figtree/>).

Parameter settings for fastsimcoal2 analysis based on the phylogenetic topology estimated from genome-wide data

An average generation time of 2.1 years for these *Emberiza* species (Bird et al. 2020) and an average passeriform mutation rate of 0.33% per My (Zhang et al. 2014) were applied. Based on the divergence time estimations (Fig. 2c), we set a search range of T10 (divergence time between southern and northern *E. godlewskii*) from 164,905 to 214,286 generations, T20 (divergence time between *E. cia* and *E. godlewskii*) from

466,667 to 509,524 generations, T30 (divergence time between *E. cioides* and the former two species) from 785,714 to 847,619 generations, and T40 (divergence time between *E. jankowskii* and the former three species) from 1,085,714 to 1,180,952 generations. The effective population sizes for all modern and ancestral populations were set between 1,000 and 10,000,000. We set a search range of gene flow from 0.0000001 to 0.1 for both directions.

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Table S1. DNA Sampling information and sequencing statistics.

Species	Sample Number	Sex	Collection Year	Longitude	Latitude	Sequencing Depth
<i>E. godlewskii</i> North	775	♂	2002	86.33	42.77	14.7
<i>E. godlewskii</i> North	3477	♂	/	113.998	36.536	15.9
<i>E. godlewskii</i> North	5087	♀	2000	115.447	39.972	17.8
<i>E. godlewskii</i> North	8683	♂	2008	112.006	35.44	15.4
<i>E. godlewskii</i> South	4119	♀	2005	101.846	27.028	14.1
<i>E. godlewskii</i> South	4872	♀	2000	99.706	27.823	14
<i>E. godlewskii</i> South	5103	♂	2000	93.655	30.932	16.4
<i>E. godlewskii</i> South	5110	♂	2000	99.747	23.225	14
<i>E. godlewskii</i> South	21435	♀	2015	93.667	29.867	17.8
<i>E. cia</i>	18321	♀	2013	72.868	38.098	14.3
<i>E. cia</i>	18342	♂	2013	72.868	38.098	14.3
<i>E. cia</i>	18344	♂	2013	72.868	38.098	15.6
<i>E. cia</i>	20253	♂	2014	71.586	39.231	17.3
<i>E. cia</i>	20254	♂	2014	71.586	39.231	16.5
<i>E. cia</i>	20255	♂	2014	71.586	39.231	15.1
<i>E. cia</i>	20273	♀	2014	70.522	38.657	16.4
<i>E. cia</i>	20278	♂	2014	70.522	38.657	15
<i>E. cia</i>	20360	♀	2014	68.871	39.056	18.7
<i>E. cia</i>	20362	♀	2014	68.871	39.056	15.7
<i>E. cia</i>	20372	♂	2014	68.871	39.056	16.9
<i>E. cioides</i>	1885	♂	2004	110.074	34.569	14.1
<i>E. cioides</i>	3419	♂	2003	126.556	43.844	13.2
<i>E. cioides</i>	3479	♂	/	113.998	36.537	13.6
<i>E. cioides</i>	4283	♀	2005	123.215	41.062	15.3
<i>E. cioides</i>	8686	♂	2008	112.006	35.44	15.2
<i>E. cioides</i>	10712	♀	2009	124.362	40.006	13.2
<i>E. cioides</i>	10728	♂	2009	124.804	40.877	14.1
<i>E. cioides</i>	10867	♂	2009	130.501	42.969	13.9
<i>E. cioides</i>	13659	♂	2010	121.676	42.028	14.4
<i>E. cioides</i>	24332	♂	2018	109.228	33.989	14.3
<i>E. jankowskii</i>	ALH01	♀	2013	119.941	45.288	21.1
<i>E. jankowskii</i>	ALH02	♀	2013	119.941	45.288	20.7
<i>E. jankowskii</i>	CG1901	♀	2019	121.183	44.475	18.5
<i>E. jankowskii</i>	CG1902	♂	2019	121.183	44.475	14
<i>E. jankowskii</i>	GHT01	♀	2013	121.085	44.932	14.2
<i>E. jankowskii</i>	GHT02	♀	2013	121.085	44.932	15.2
<i>E. jankowskii</i>	KD1301	♂	2013	119.92	44.273	18.5
<i>E. jankowskii</i>	KD1302	♀	2013	119.92	44.273	19.1
<i>E. jankowskii</i>	LB1301	♀	2013	120.899	44.56	15.4
<i>E. jankowskii</i>	LB1302	♂	2013	120.899	44.56	15.5
<i>E. stewarti</i>	20271	♀	2014	70.52	38.66	19.1

E. godlewskii North and *E. godlewskii* South represent the northern and southern populations of *E. godlewskii*, respectively.

Table S2. A summary of parameters in phylogenomic analyses, population structure analyses and gene flow tests.

Method	Input data	Model
Dsuite	20,994,339 autosomal SNVs	/
IQ-TREE	2,654,187 out of 20,994,339 concatenated autosomal linkage-pruned homozygous variants (with heterozygous sites deleted)	GTR+ASC
RAxML	47,547 autosomal consensus sequences of 20 Kb sliding windows	GTRGAMMA
MP-EST	20,000 out of 47,547 autosomal trees generated from RAxML analysis	/
RAxML-NG	3,583 Z chromosomal consensus sequences of 20 Kb sliding windows for all individuals; 47,562 autosomal and 3,732 Z chromosomal consensus alignments for only 1 individual from each clade	GTR+G
ASTRAL	3,583 Z chromosomal trees generated from RAxML-NG analysis	/
StarBEAST2	100 out of 47,547 autosomal consensus sequences	GTR
FRAPPE/PCA	5,407,601 out of 20,994,339 autosomal linkage-pruned SNVs	/
fastsimcoal2	5,407,601 out of 20,994,339 autosomal linkage-pruned SNVs	/

Table S3. Dsuite analysis result.

P1	P2	P3	Dstatistic	f4-ratio	p-value
<i>E. cia</i>	<i>E. cioides</i>	<i>E. jankowskii</i>	0.1035	0.0446	0
<i>E. godlewskii</i> North	<i>E. cioides</i>	<i>E. jankowskii</i>	0.0699	0.0284	0
<i>E. godlewskii</i> South	<i>E. cioides</i>	<i>E. jankowskii</i>	0.0810	0.0339	0
<i>E. cia</i>	<i>E. godlewskii</i> North	<i>E. jankowskii</i>	0.0494	0.0166	0
<i>E. godlewskii</i> South	<i>E. godlewskii</i> North	<i>E. jankowskii</i>	0.0173	0.0056	0
<i>E. cia</i>	<i>E. godlewskii</i> South	<i>E. jankowskii</i>	0.0339	0.0111	0
<i>E. cia</i>	<i>E. godlewskii</i> North	<i>E. cioides</i>	0.163888	0.1344	0
<i>E. godlewskii</i> South	<i>E. godlewskii</i> North	<i>E. cioides</i>	0.0794	0.0675	0
<i>E. cia</i>	<i>E. godlewskii</i> South	<i>E. cioides</i>	0.0927	0.0718	0
<i>E. godlewskii</i> North	<i>E. godlewskii</i> South	<i>E. cia</i>	0.0315	0.0250	0

E. godlewskii South and *E. godlewskii* North represent the southern and northern populations of *E. godlewskii*, respectively. F4-ratio represents admixture proportion.

Table S4. Observed and estimated likelihood and AIC values for all 12 models in figure S5 tested in fastsimcoal2. The best fit models with the highest likelihood and lowest AIC are indicated in bold.

Model	Maximum observed likelihood	Maximum estimated likelihood	AIC
Model 1-1	-55,603,545	-60,273,212	277,568,434
Model 1-2	-55,603,545	-60,263,855	277,525,343
Model 1-3	-55,603,545	-60,334,537	277,850,851
Model 1-4	-55,603,545	-60,631,459	279,218,216
Model 2-1	-55,603,545	-60,457,414	278,416,715
Model 2-2	-55,603,545	-60,989,965	280,869,203
Model 2-3	-55,603,545	-60,465,002	278,451,662
Model 2-4	-55,603,545	-60,732,842	279,685,104
Model 3-1	-55,603,545	-60,769,483	279,853,845
Model 3-2	-55,603,545	-60,310,268	277,739,082
Model 3-3	-55,603,545	-60,489,991	278,566,739
Model 3-4	-55,603,545	-60,675,620	279,421,585

The smaller the difference between Maximum observed likelihood and Maximum estimated likelihood, the better the model.

Table S5. Observed and estimated likelihood and AIC values for all 6 models in figure S1 tested in fastsimcoal2. The best fit model with the highest likelihood and lowest AIC is indicated in bold.

Model	Maximum observed likelihood	Maximum estimated likelihood	AIC
Model a	-55,603,545	-59,735,225	275,090,932
Model b	-55,603,545	-59,875,124	275,735,187
Model c	-55,603,545	-59,461,191	273,828,954
Model d	-55,603,545	-59,964,874	276,148,505
Model e	-55,603,545	-60,129,159	276,905,053
Model f	-55,603,545	-60,449,490	278,380,219

The smaller the difference between Maximum observed likelihood and Maximum estimated likelihood, the better the model.

Table S6. Parameters estimated in fastsimcoal2 for model c in figure S1.

Parameter	Value
T10	187,643 generations
T20	494,603 generations
T30	819,297 generations
T40	1,151,126 generations
θ_n	20,449
θ_s	53,629
θ_{cia}	755,039
θ_{cio}	1,050,047
θ_{jank}	50,919
θ_{sn}	5,839
θ_{snc}	66,060
θ_{sncc}	2,699,824
θ_a	3,144,905
Mig03	1.72E-07
Mig30	1.22E-05
Mig04	8.02E-05
Mig40	2.03E-06
Mig12	2.71E-05
Mig21	7.82E-07
Mig14	2.58E-05
Mig41	1.45E-05
Mig34	1.26E-07
Mig43	1.79E-05

Mig03 represents migration from the ancestral population of *E. godlewskii* into *E. cioides*, while Mig30 represents the opposite migration direction. Mig04 represents migration from northern *E. godlewskii* into *E. jankowskii*, while Mig40 represents the opposite migration direction. Mig12 represents migration from southern *E. godlewskii* into *E. cia*, while Mig21 represents the opposite migration direction. Mig14 represents migration from southern *E. godlewskii* into *E. jankowskii*, while Mig41 represents the opposite migration direction. Mig34 represents migration from *E. cioides* into *E. jankowskii*, while Mig43 represents the opposite migration direction. See Figure S3 for other parameters.

Figure S1. 12 simplified models tested in fastsimcoal2 to identify the most likely species tree among the three most frequent gene trees (a) tree 1, (b) tree 2 and (c) tree 3. (a) If tree 1 represents the true species tree, gene flow between *E. cia* and southern *E. godlewskii* (model 1-1) as well as between *E. cia* and northern *E. godlewskii* (model 1-2), in conjunction with incomplete lineage sorting (ILS), may lead to the occurrence of tree 2 and tree 3; these two kinds of gene flow may exist simultaneously (model 1-3); in the absence of gene flow, tree 2 and tree 3 can also arise solely due to ILS (model 1-4). (b) If tree 2 represents the true species tree, gene flow between northern and southern *E. godlewskii* (model 2-1) as well as between *E. cia* and northern *E. godlewskii* (model 2-2), in conjunction with ILS, may lead to the occurrence of tree 1 and tree 3; these two kinds of gene flow may exist simultaneously (model 2-3); in the absence of gene flow, tree 1 and tree 3 can also arise solely due to ILS (model 2-4). (c) If tree 3 represents the true species tree, gene flow between *E. cia* and southern *E. godlewskii* (model 3-1) as well as between northern and southern *E. godlewskii* (model 3-2), in conjunction with ILS, may lead to the occurrence of tree 1 and tree 2; these two kinds of gene flow may exist simultaneously (model 3-3); in the absence of gene flow, tree 1 and tree 2 can also arise solely due to ILS (model 3-4). T_s and θ_s represent divergence times and population sizes, respectively. The labels *godl. north* and *godl. south* represent the northern and southern *E. godlewskii* populations, respectively.

Figure S2. Six tested divergence models in fastsimcoal2 on the basis of the most likely species tree.

(a) Divergence model with gene flow between *E. jankowskii*/*E. cioides* and both northern and southern *E. godlewskii*, between southern *E. godlewskii* and *E. cia*, between *E. jankowskii* and *E. cioides* before T10. (b) Divergence model with gene flow between *E. cioides* and both northern and southern *E. godlewskii*, between southern *E. godlewskii* and *E. cia*, between *E. jankowskii* and *E. cioides* before T10, and between *E. jankowskii* and the ancestral lineage of *E. godlewskii* between T10 and T20. (c) Divergence model with gene flow between *E. jankowskii* and both northern and southern *E. godlewskii*, between southern *E. godlewskii* and *E. cia*, between *E. jankowskii* and *E. cioides* before T10, and between *E. cioides* and the ancestral lineage of *E. godlewskii* between T10 and T20. (d) Divergence model with gene flow between southern *E. godlewskii* and *E. cia*, between *E. jankowskii* and *E. cioides* before T10, and between *E. cioides*/*E. jankowskii* and the ancestral lineage of *E. godlewskii* between T10 and T20. T10, T20, T30 and T40 represent divergence times between southern and northern *E. godlewskii*, between *E. godlewskii* and *E. cia*, between *E. cioides* and the former two species, and the root divergence time, respectively. θ_s , θ_n , θ_{cia} , θ_{cio} , θ_{jank} represent population sizes of southern and northern *E. godlewskii*, *E. cia*, *E. cioides* and *E. jankowskii*, respectively. θ_{sn} , θ_{snc} , θ_{sncc} and θ_a represent ancestral population sizes before lineage splits.

Figure S3. ASTRAL analysis result using 3,583 Z chromosomal gene trees. Posterior probabilities are shown above the nodes, with asterisks representing a posterior probability of 1.00. The labels *godlewskii* North and *godlewskii* South represent the northern and southern *E. godlewskii* populations, respectively. The tree was rooted with the outgroup (*E. stewarti*) in FigTree.

Figure S4. Ten main tree topologies among 1,881 trees in which each of the five *Emberiza* lineages emerges as monophyletic, based on 20 Kb sliding-window phylogenetic analyses in RAXML. The abbreviations *jank.* and *godl.* represent *E. jankowskii* and *E. godlewskii*, respectively.

Figure S5. The distribution and proportions of the main phylogenetic topologies across the autosomes and Z chromosome based on 20 Kb sliding window analysis in RAxML-NG using only one individual from each clade. Only tree topologies with a proportion >3% are displayed for both the autosomes and Z chromosome. Alternating colors on each chromosome correspond to the tree topologies with the same colors displayed in the panel; blank spaces are missing values. The histograms represent the proportions of each tree topology on autosomes and the Z chromosome. The abbreviations *jank.* and *godl.* represent *E. jankowskii* and *E. godlewskii*, respectively. Chromosome number is shown on the vertical axis, while the horizontal axis represents chromosomes' length scaled in base pairs (bp).

Figure S6. Comparisons of AIC values by running each model with the best parameter values from the best run. AICs of model c were significantly lower than other models. *** $p < 0.001$ estimated by Wilcoxon rank sum test.

Figure S7. Alignment result between the W chromosome of *Taeniopygia guttata* and the NRW sequences of *Ficedula albicollis* using NGenomeSyn. The range between the farthest aligned points (black vertical lines) on the W chromosome of *Taeniopygia guttata* was considered as the range of potential NRW sequences (~20.3 Mb).